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EKSTRAKCIJA FOSFORA POMOĆU OKSALNE KISELINE IZ PEPELA DOBIJENOG POSTUPKOM SPALJIVANJA MULJA

PHOSPHORUS REGENERATION FROM INCINERATED SEWAGE SLUDGE ASH (ISSA) BY USING OXALIC ACID

IZVOD

Fosfor (P) je esencijalan element za sve žive organizme. Primjenjuje se u industriji, naročito u proizvodnji vještačkih đubriva, koja su od vitalne važnosti za globalnu proizvodnju hrane. Međutim, fosfatne rude, iz kojih se fosfor uglavnom ekstrahuje, su neobnovljiv resurs. Problem pri upotrebi fosfatnih đubriva je njihov visok nivo neiskorišćenosti (oko 80%), što izaziva eutrofikaciju u vodenim ekosistemima. Stoga, rekuperacija fosfora postaje neophodna. Regeneracija fosfora iz muljnog pepela zahtjeva efikasne metode koje će izolovati fosfor i odvojiti ga od kontaminanata, čineći ga lako dostupnim za dalju upotrebu. Mokra hemijska ekstrakcija sa organskim kiselinama ima sve veću primjenu, pa je u ovom radu praćena ekstrakcija fosfora pomoću oksalne kiseline iz muljnog pepela dobijenog spaljivanjem mulja. Analizirani su uticaji vremena ekstrakcije i koncentracije oksalne kiseline na efikasnost procesa ekstrakcije fosfora. Rezultati istraživanja su pokazali da je najviša efikasnost ekstrakcije (preko 96%) postignuta pri koncentraciji oksalne kiseline od $0,2 \text{ mol/dm}^3$ i vremenu ekstrakcije od 240 minuta.

Ključne riječi: fosfor, ekstrakcija, muljni pepeo, spaljivanje mulja, oksalna kiselina.

ABSTRACT

Phosphorus (P) is an essential element for all living organisms. It is widely used in industry, particularly in the production of synthetic fertilizers, which are crucial for global food production. However, phosphate ores, from which phosphorus is primarily extracted, are a non-renewable resource. A major issue with the use of phosphate fertilizers is their high level of inefficiency (around 80%), which leads to eutrophication in aquatic ecosystems. Therefore, phosphorus recovery has become necessary. Regeneration of phosphorus from incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA) requires efficient methods that isolate phosphorus and separate it from contaminants, making it easily available for further use. Wet chemical extraction using organic acids is increasingly applied, and in this study, phosphorus extraction using oxalic acid from sewage sludge ash obtained by incineration of sludge was investigated. The effects of extraction time and oxalic acid concentration on the efficiency of the phosphorus extraction process were analyzed. The research results showed that the highest extraction efficiency (over 96%) was achieved with an oxalic acid concentration of 0.2 mol/dm^3 and an extraction time of 240 minutes.

Keywords: phosphorus, extraction, ISSA, incineration, oxalic acid.

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1. UVOD

Fosfor (P) predstavlja makronutrijent koji je neophodan za pravilno funkcionisanje svih živih organizama. Važan je za sintezu DNK u ćelijskim membranama, za akumulaciju energije u vidu ATP-a, kao i za obrazovanje zuba i kostiju kod ljudi. Pored toga, fosfor ima značajnu industrijsku i poljoprivrednu ulogu, jer se u velikoj mjeri, zajedno sa azotom i kalijumom, upotrebljava za proizvodnju vještačkih đubriva, neophodnih za globalnu proizvodnju hrane (Cheng et al., 2023; Cho, 2013; Liang et al., 2019).

Trenutno se fosfor najčešće proizvodi preradom fosfatnih ruda, koje su neobnovljiv resurs, i u Zemljinoj kori su prisutne u veoma malim količinama (oko 0,09%). Fosfatne rude se prvenstveno prerađuju u fosfatna đubriva, koja imaju dalju primjenu u proizvodnji hrane i mesa. Oko 80% fosfatnih đubriva biva neiskorišteno i odlazi u prirodne vodotokove, gdje se kao posljedica porasta koncentracije fosfora u vodenim ekosistemima, javlja eutrofikacija (Filippelli, 2008; Peng et al., 2018; Witek-Krowiak et al., 2022). Smatra se da će sadašnje zalihe fosfatnih ruda biti eksploatisane u narednih 50 do 100 godina (Cordell et al., 2009; Luyckx et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2012), te je stoga rekuperacija fosfora od izuzetne važnosti.

Iako danas većina postrojenja za preradu otpadnih voda koristi unaprijeđeno biološko uklanjanje fosfora (eng. Enhanced Biological Phosphorus Removal-EBPR), ili proces hemijskog uklanjanja fosfora, oko 90 % fosfora na kraju završi u otpadnom mulju. Mulj dobijen na ovaj način se ne može direktno koristiti u poljoprivredne svrhe zbog povećane koncentracije teških metala (Wang et al., 2018) i drugih organskih i neorganskih materija (Liang et al., 2019), a pored toga fosfor u ovom obliku nije dostupan biljkama (Ottosen et al., 2013).

Regeneracija fosfora se može izvesti i iz pepela nastalog monoincineracijom mulja, kao sekundarnog izvora fosfora, jer se spaljivanjem mulja, fosfor najvećim dijelom koncentriše u pepelu. Monoincineracija mulja predstavlja metodu spaljivanja (incineracije) pri kojoj se obezvodnjeni mulj izlaže visokim temperaturama u postrojenjima za spaljivanje, specijalno konstruisanim za ovu namjenu. Kao proizvod monoincineracije se dobijaju pepeo i para. Na ovaj način proizveden muljni pepeo sadrži od 3,5 do 12 % fosfora, što je slično sadržaju fosfora u niskokvalitetnim fosfatnim rudama (Fang et al., 2018; Kerkez & Kulić-Mandić, 2022; Luyckx et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018). Metode koje se koriste za regeneraciju fosfora iz muljnog pepela trebaju

1. INTRODUCTION

Phosphorus (P) is a macronutrient essential for the proper functioning of all living organisms. It is important for DNA synthesis in cell membranes, for the accumulation of energy in the form of ATP, and for the formation of teeth and bones in humans. In addition, phosphorus plays a significant industrial and agricultural role, as it is extensively used, along with nitrogen and potassium, in the production of artificial fertilizers, which are essential for global food production (Cheng et al., 2023; Cho, 2013; Liang et al., 2019).

Currently, phosphorus is most commonly produced by processing phosphate ores, which are a non-renewable resource and are present in the Earth's crust in very small quantities (around 0.09%). Phosphate ores are primarily processed into phosphate fertilizers, which are further used in food and meat production. Approximately 80% of phosphate fertilizers are not utilized and end up in natural water systems, where, as a result of increased phosphorus concentrations in aquatic ecosystems, eutrophication occurs (Filippelli, 2008; Peng et al., 2018; Witek-Krowiak et al., 2022). It is believed that current phosphate ore reserves will be exhausted within the next 50 to 100 years (Cordell et al., 2009; Luyckx et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2012), making phosphorus recovery of great importance.

Although most wastewater treatment plants today use enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) or chemical phosphorus removal processes, around 90% of phosphorus ultimately ends up in sewage sludge. This sludge cannot be directly used for agricultural purposes due to the increased concentration of heavy metals (Wang et al., 2018) and other organic and inorganic substances (Liang et al., 2019), and moreover, phosphorus in this form is not available to plants (Ottosen et al., 2013).

Phosphorus regeneration can also be carried out from the ash produced by the mono-incineration of sludge, as a secondary phosphorus source, because during sludge incineration, phosphorus is largely concentrated in the ash. The mono-incineration of sludge represents a combustion (incineration) method in which dewatered sludge is exposed to high temperatures in combustion facilities specifically designed for this purpose. The products of mono-incineration are ash and steam. Ash produced in this manner contains between 3.5 and 12% phosphorus, which is similar to the phosphorus content in low-quality phosphate ores (Fang et al., 2018; Kerkez & Kulić-Mandić, 2022; Luyckx et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018). Methods used for phosphorus regeneration

da zadovolje sljedeće uslove (Kerkez i Kulić-Mandić, 2022):

- a. da povećaju koncentraciju fosfora;
- b. da prevedu fosfor u fosfatno đubrivo dostupno biljkama (Li et al., 2020) ili u fosforu kiselinu (industrijska upotreba) (Donatello et al., 2010)
- c. da odvoje fosfor od kontaminanata poput teških metala i ostalih nepoželjnih supstanci (aluminijum, gvožđe) sadržanih u pepelu (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013).

Postoji nekoliko metoda koje se koriste za regeneraciju fosfora (Li et al., 2020) iz muljnog pepela među kojima se najčešće koriste termohemijska metoda (Hu et al., 2023; Pasalari et al., 2024), elektrodijalitička remedijacija-EDR (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013; Fang et al., 2023) i hemijska ekstrakcija (Donatello et al., 2010; Kleemann, 2016; Petzet et al., 2012). Od navedenih metoda, najširu primjenu ima mokra hemijska ekstrakcija zbog jednostavnosti i niske cijene izvođenja (Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2020). Ekstrakcija se uglavnom izvodi primjenom sljedećih reagenasa za ekstrakciju (Biswas et al., 2009; Li et al., 2020): neorganske kiseline (Kleemann et al., 2017), neorganske soli (Hu et al., 2023), organske kiseline (Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2020), alkalne supstance (Takahashi et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2018) i helatna sredstva (Fang et al., 2018b). Najveća efikasnost ekstrakcije fosfora se ostvaruje pri upotrebi neorganskih kiselina koje ujedno dovode do luženja i teških metala zajedno sa fosforom, te je neophodno dodatno prečišćavanje ekstrakta fosfora (Li et al., 2020).

Organske kiseline također posjeduju relativno visoku sposobnost ekstrakcije fosfora iz muljnog pepela, te stoga imaju široku primjenu kod procesa luženja fosfora (Fang et al., 2018b). Organska kiselina koja pokazuje izuzetno visoku efikasnost ekstrakcije fosfora je oksalna kiselina. Pripada grupi jakih organskih kiselina ($pK_a = 1,252$), te zbog svojih redukcionih svojstava doprinosi boljoj ekstrakciji fosfora iz muljnog pepela. (Abis et al., 2018; Atienza-Martínez, et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2021). Osim toga, oksalna kiselina je prisutna u tkivima mnogih biljaka i algi, te nema negativan uticaj na životnu sredinu (USEPA, 1992).

Cilj ovog istraživanja je bio ispitivanje mogućnosti ekstrakcije fosfora primjenom oksalne kiseline iz muljnog pepela dobijenog nakon monocineracije mulja sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadne vode, kao i uticaj vremena ekstrakcije i koncentracije oksalne kiseline na efikasnost ekstrakcije fosfora.

from incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA) must meet the following criteria (Kerkez & Kulić-Mandić, 2022):

- a. Increase the phosphorus concentration;
- b. Convert phosphorus into phosphate fertilizer available to plants (Li et al., 2020) or into phosphoric acid (for industrial use) (Donatello et al., 2010);
- c. Separate phosphorus from contaminants such as heavy metals and other undesirable substances (aluminum, iron) present in the ash (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013).

There are several methods used for phosphorus regeneration (Li et al., 2020) from ISSA, among which the most commonly used are thermochemical methods (Hu et al., 2023; Pasalari et al., 2024), electrodiolytic remediation (EDR) (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013; Fang et al., 2023), and chemical extraction (Donatello et al., 2010; Kleemann, 2016; Petzet et al., 2012). Among these methods, wet chemical extraction is the most widely used due to its simplicity and low cost (Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2020). Extraction is usually carried out using the following extraction reagents (Biswas et al., 2009; Li et al., 2020): inorganic acids (Kleemann et al., 2017), inorganic salts (Hu et al., 2023), organic acids (Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2020), alkaline substances (Takahashi et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2018), and chelating agents (Fang et al., 2018b). The highest extraction efficiency of phosphorus is achieved using inorganic acids, which also provokes leaching of heavy metals along with phosphorus, thus requiring further purification of the phosphorus extract (Li et al., 2020).

Organic acids also possess relatively high phosphorus extraction capabilities from ISSA, and as such, they have a wide application in phosphorus leaching processes (Fang et al., 2018b). One of the organic acids that demonstrates exceptionally high phosphorus extraction efficiency is oxalic acid. It belongs to the group of strong organic acids ($pK_a = 1.252$) and, due to its reductive properties, contributes to better phosphorus extraction from ISSA (Abis et al., 2018; Atienza-Martínez et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2019; Luyckx et al., 2021). Furthermore, oxalic acid is present in the tissues of many plants and algae, and thus has no negative impact on the environment (USEPA, 1992).

The aim of this research was to examine the potential for phosphorus extraction using oxalic acid from the incinerated sewage sludge ash from wastewater treatment plants, as well as the impact of extraction time and oxalic acid concentration on the phosphorus extraction efficiency.

2. MATERIJALI I METODE

Kao polazni materijal za ispitivanje mogućnosti ekstrakcije fosfora korišten je pepeo, dobijen spaljivanjem mulja sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadne vode kapaciteta 150.000 ES, na temperaturi od 850°C. U okviru postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, minimalni kapacitet postrojenja je 150.000 ES, a sadašnji (trenutni) kapacitet je približno 110.000 ES. Hidrauličko opterećenje (količina otpadne vode) za normalni dnevni kapacitet: za suvi period – 36.000 m³/dan, za kišni period – 72.000 m³/dan, odnosno 1100 m³/h kao stvarna časovna vrijednost. Postrojenje sadrži liniju vode i liniju mulja. Na liniji vode se prvo vrši mehaničko prečišćavanje i predtretman otpadne vode, a zatim se vrši biološko prečišćavanje aktivnim muljem. Na liniji mulja se vrši tretman nastalih muljeva prilikom procesa prečišćavanja otpadnih voda, pri čemu kao proizvodi nastaju biogas i stabilizovani mulj. Tretmani u okviru linije mulja podrazumijevaju ugušćivanje primarnog mulja u gravitacionim ugušćivačima; ugušćivanje viška mulja uz dodavanje rastvora polielektrolita; jednostepenu aerobnu digestiju mulja radi stabilizacije nastalog mulja prilikom biološkog prečišćavanja; obezvodnjavanje digestovanog mulja na trakastoj filter presi do sadržaja suve materije oko 20-24%.

Sadržaj suve i organske materije je određen sušenjem 5 g uzorka na 105°C do konstante mase, a zatim i žarenjem na 550°C kako bi se odredio gubitak mase žarenjem u skladu sa takozvanom NEN procedurom holandskog instituta za standardizaciju (eng. Netherlands Normalisation Institute): NEN 5754 (%W) (NEN 5754).

Pseudo-ukupni sadržaj metala u muljnom pepelu je određen primjenom digestije po metodi EPA 3051a (USEPA 3051A, 2007) mikrotalasnom digestijom (Milestone, star E), a zatim su uzorci analizirani tehnikom indukovanu spregnute plazme sa masenom spektroskopijom – ICP-MS (Perkin Elmer Sciek Elan 5000) u skladu sa USEPA metodom 6020B (USEPA 6020b, 2014).

Pepeo je potom usitnjen, i prosijan, pri čemu je za dalje izvođenje eksperimenta odabrana fina frakcija pepela (-56 μm).

Ekstrakcija fosfora iz muljnog pepela izvedena je upotrebom rastvora oksalne kiseline, različitih početnih koncentracija (0,1, 0,2, 0,3, 0,4, 0,5M). Za pravljenje rastvora oksalne kiseline korišten je dihidrat oksalne kiseline (H₂C₂O₄·2H₂O), analitičke čistoće. Postupak ekstrakcije fosfora je izveden u šaržnim uslovima. U plastične kivete je dodato 20 mL rastvora oksalne kiseline poznate koncentracije, tako da je odnos rastvora oksalne kiseline i pepela bio isti u svim ekstrakcijama, i iznosio je 20:1. Nakon pripreme suspenzije, kivete su zavrtnute, i stavljene

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As the starting material for examining the possibility of phosphorus extraction, ash obtained by combustion of sludge from a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) with a capacity of 150,000 population equivalent, PE, was used, at a temperature of 850°C. Within the WWTP, the nominal capacity is 150,000 PE, while the actual capacity is approximately 110,000 PE. The hydraulic load (the amount of wastewater) for the normal daily capacity is: for dry periods – 36,000 m³/day, for rainy periods – 72,000 m³/day, or 1,100 m³/h as the actual hourly value. The plant includes both, a water line and a sludge line. The water line first undergoes mechanical treatment and pretreatment of the wastewater, followed by biological treatment using activated sludge. The sludge line involves the treatment of sludge produced during the wastewater treatment process, resulting in biogas and stabilized sludge as by-products. The treatments within the sludge line include thickening of primary sludge in gravity thickeners, thickening of excess sludge with the addition of a poly-electrolyte solution, single-stage aerobic digestion of the sludge to stabilize the sludge generated during biological treatment, and dewatering of the digested sludge on a belt filter press to a dry matter content of around 20-24%.

The content of dry and organic matter was determined by drying a 5 g sample at 105°C to constant weight, followed by ignition at 550°C to determine the loss of ignition according to the so-called NEN procedure by the Royal Netherlands Normalization Institute (NNI): NEN 5754 (%W) (NEN 5754).

The pseudo-total metal content in the sludge ash was determined using digestion by the EPA 3051a method (USEPA 3051A, 2007) via microwave digestion (Milestone, star E), followed by analysis of the samples using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy - ICP-MS (Perkin Elmer Sciek Elan 5000) according to the USEPA method 6020B (USEPA 6020b, 2014).

The ash was then crushed and sieved, with the fine fraction of the ash (-56 μm) selected for further experimentation.

Phosphorus extraction from the ISSA was performed using oxalic acid solutions of varying initial concentrations (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5M). Oxalic acid dihydrate (H₂C₂O₄·2H₂O) of analytical purity was used to prepare the oxalic acid solutions. The phosphorus extraction procedure was carried out in batch conditions. 20 mL of the oxalic acid solution of known concentration was added to plastic cuvettes, ensuring a consistent oxalic acid-to-ash ratio of 20:1 across all extractions. After preparing the suspension,

na horizontalni laboratorijski šejker, gdje su se mučkale pri brzini od 120 rpm određeni vremenski period. Ekstrakcija fosfora je praćena u sljedećim vremenskim intervalima: 30, 120, 240 i 1440 minuta. Razdvajanje čvrste i tečne faze izvršeno je, nakon ekstrakcije, centrifugiranjem u trajanju od 15 minuta, pri 6000 rpm na laboratorijskoj centrifugi, a potom i filtriranjem pomoću plave filter trake. Sadržaj fosfora u dobijenim ekstraktima je određen primjenom tehnike indukovanu spregnute plazme sa optičkom emisionom spektroskopijom (ICP-OES) prema metodi ISO 11885:2007 (ISO 11885, 2007).

3. REZULTATI I ZAPAŽANJA

Procenat suve materije u uzorku mulja iznosi oko 22%, dok je u uzorku muljnog pepela procenat vlage očekivano mali (0,5% za pepeo). Poređenjem sa rezultatima iz drugih literaturnih izvora, kod koji je sadržaj vode bio visok (76,4%), dokazujemo da izmjerena vrijednost suve materije (22%) ulazi u opseg između 15 i 30% koji se predstavlja kao optimalan (Pöykiö et al., 2019). Svakako, sadržaj suve materije zavisi od vrste mulja i procesa tretmana koji mogu smanjiti sadržaj vode i na taj način povećati procenat čvrstih materija.

Na osnovu vrijednosti hemijskog sastava muljnog pepela predstavljenih u tabeli 1, muljni pepeo sadrži značajnu količinu ukupnog fosfora (160,55 mg/g), pa samim tim predstavlja materijal pogodan za ekstrakciju fosfora. Pošto su u muljnom pepelu prisutne značajne količine gvožđa (2,3444 mg/g), aluminijuma (1,4999 mg/g) i mangana (0,4923 mg/g), potrebno je obratiti pažnju na mogućnost luženja ovih metala pri ekstrakciji fosfora sa oksalnom kiselinom.

Vrijednosti efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora pomoću oksalne kiseline iz muljnog pepela dobijenog incineracijom su prikazani na slikama 1 i 2. Svaka ekstrakcija je izvedena pri konstantom odnosu tečno/čvrsto (L/S odnos) od 20/1. L/S odnos je važan parametar, posebno u ekonomskom pogledu, obzirom da veći L/S odnos podrazumijeva upotrebu reaktora za ekstrakciju fosfora većih dimenzija (Luyckx et al., 2019). Kod svih dobijenih ekstrakata fosfora je ostvarena efikasnost ekstrakcije iznad 50%. Osim toga, spaljivanje mulja je izvedeno na 850°C zbog čega može doći do sinterovanja i topljenja čestica gvožđa i silicijuma prisutnih u pepelu, koji onemogućavaju prodiranje kiseline unutar pora pepela i reakciju sa jedinjenjima koja sadže fosfor, i samim tim nešto niže vrijednosti stepena ekstrakcije od očekivanih (Atienza–Martínez, et al., 2014; Li et al., 2020; Luyckx et al., 2019; Liang et al., 2021).

the cuvettes were capped and placed on a horizontal laboratory shaker, where they were shaken at 120 rpm for specific periods of time. Phosphorus extraction was monitored at the following time intervals: 30, 120, 240, and 1440 minutes. After extraction, the solid and liquid phases were separated by centrifugation for 15 minutes at 6000 rpm using a laboratory centrifuge, followed by filtration using a blue filter tape. The phosphorus content in the resulting extracts was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) according to the ISO 11885:2007 method (ISO 11885, 2007).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The percentage of dry matter in the sludge sample is approximately 22%, while the moisture content in the incinerated sewage sludge ash sample is predictably low (0.5% for ash). Compared to results from other literature sources, where the water content was high (76.4%), we can demonstrate that the measured dry matter value (22%) falls within the range of 15-30%, which is considered optimal (Pöykiö et al., 2019). Certainly, the dry matter content depends on the type of sludge and the treatment processes, which can reduce water content and thus increase the percentage of solid materials.

Based on the chemical composition values of the ISSA presented in Table 1, the ash contains a significant amount of total phosphorus (160.55 mg/g), making it a material suitable for phosphorus extraction. Since significant amounts of iron (2.3444 mg/g), aluminum (1.4999 mg/g), and manganese (0.4923 mg/g) are present in the ISSA, attention should be paid to the potential leaching of these metals during phosphorus extraction with oxalic acid.

The values of phosphorus extraction efficiency using oxalic acid from ISSA obtained by incineration are presented in Figures 1 and 2. Each extraction was performed at a constant liquid/solid (L/S) ratio of 20/1. The L/S ratio is an important parameter, especially from an economic perspective, as a higher L/S ratio implies the use of larger reactors for phosphorus extraction (Luyckx et al., 2019). For all obtained phosphorus extracts, the extraction efficiency exceeded 50%. Additionally, since the sludge was incinerated at 850°C, sintering and melting of iron and silicon particles present in the ash may occur, which hinders the penetration of the acid into the ash pores and its reaction with compounds containing phosphorus, leading to somewhat lower extraction efficiency values than expected (Atienza–Martínez et al., 2014; Li et al., 2020; Luyckx et al., 2019; Liang et al., 2021).

Tabela 1 Hemijski sastav muljnog pepela dobijenog spaljivanjem mulja

	Sadržaj u muljnom pepelu
B	6,5591 µg/g
Al	1,4999 mg/g
P	160,055 mg/g
Cr	6,4502 µg/g
Mn	0,4923 mg/g
Fe	2,3444 mg/g
Co	0,6713 µg/g
Ni	3,5835 µg/g
Cu	16,715 µg/g
Zn	55,474 µg/g
As	7,5016 µg/g
Se	0,2355 µg/g
Ag	0,0997 µg/g
Cd	0,0850 µg/g
Pb	5,2655 µg/g
%W	0,5%

Table 1. Chemical composition of ISSA obtained by incineration

	Content of the ISSA
B	6.5591 µg/g
Al	1.4999 mg/g
P	160.055 mg/g
Cr	6.4502 µg/g
Mn	0.4923 mg/g
Fe	2.3444 mg/g
Co	0.6713 µg/g
Ni	3.5835 µg/g
Cu	16.715 µg/g
Zn	55.474 µg/g
As	7.5016 µg/g
Se	0.2355 µg/g
Ag	0.0997 µg/g
Cd	0.0850 µg/g
Pb	5.2655 µg/g
%W	0.5 %

Kao što je prikazano na slici 1, pri vremenu ekstrakcije od 240 minuta dostižu se najveće vrijednosti efikasnosti ekstrakcije, nezavisno od koncentracije oksalne kiseline. Daljim produženjem vremena ekstrakcije, dolazi do pada efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora ispod 80%, što može biti posljedica luženja teških metala i ostalih primjesa prisutnih u pepelu. Obzirom da su u pepelu prisutne značajne količine gvožđa i aluminijuma (tabela 1), pri dužem trajanju ekstrakcije, dolazi do obrazovanja kompleksa između oksalnih jona i Fe^{3+}/Al^{3+} jona (Liang et al., 2019). Smanjenje efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora pri vremenu ekstrakcije od 1440 minuta, može biti upravo posljedica smanjenja dostupnosti oksalne kiseline za reakciju sa jedinjenjima koja sadrže fosfor.

As shown in Figure 1, the highest extraction efficiency values are reached at an extraction time of 240 minutes, regardless of the oxalic acid concentration. Further increasing the extraction time results in a decrease in phosphorus extraction efficiency below 80%, which may be due to the leaching of heavy metals and other impurities present in the ash. Since significant amounts of iron and aluminum are present in the ash (Table 1), during longer extraction times, complexes may form between oxalate ions and Fe^{3+}/Al^{3+} ions (Liang et al., 2019). The decrease in phosphorus extraction efficiency at an extraction time of 1440 minutes may be due to the reduced availability of oxalic acid for reacting with phosphorus-containing compounds.

Slika 1 Uticaj vremena ekstrakcije na efikasnost ekstrakcije fosfora

Figure 1. Effect of extraction time on phosphorus extraction efficiency

Procesi koji postižu regeneraciju fosfora ispod 80% mogli bi se smatrati tehnološki inferiornim ili energetski neefikasnim. Stoga, prema literaturnim podacima minimalni procent regeneracije fosfora iz muljnog pepela bi trebao biti iznad 80% (Luyckx et al., 2019).

S obzirom da je jedino pri vremenu od 240 minuta postignuta efikasnost ekstrakcije iznad 80%, na slici 2 je prikazana zavisnost efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora pri različitim koncentracijama oksalne kiseline samo u trajanju od 240 minuta. Pri koncentraciji oksalne kiseline od 0,2 mol/dm³, postiže se efikasnost ekstrakcije od 96,05%. Neznatno niže vrijednosti efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora koje su dobijene pri ostalim koncentracijama oksalne kiseline mogu biti posljedica nehomogenosti uzorka muljnog pepela.

Processes that achieve phosphorus regeneration below 80% could be considered technologically inferior or energy-inefficient. Therefore, according to the literature, the minimum percentage of phosphorus regeneration from ISSA should be above 80% (Luyckx et al., 2019).

Since extraction efficiency above 80% was only achieved at an extraction time of 240 minutes, Figure 2 shows the dependence of phosphorus extraction efficiency at different oxalic acid concentrations only for the 240-minute extraction duration. At an oxalic acid concentration of 0.2 mol/dm³, an extraction efficiency of 96.05% is achieved. The slightly lower phosphorus extraction efficiency values obtained at other oxalic acid concentrations may be due to sample inhomogeneity of the ISSA.

Slika 2 Uticaj koncentracije oksalne kiseline na efikasnost ekstrakcije fosfora u trajanju od 240 min

Figure 2. Effect of oxalic acid concentration on phosphorus extraction efficiency over a 240-minute period

4. ZAKLJUČAK

Na osnovu rezultata istraživanja dobijenih u ovom radu moguće je ekstrahovati fosfor iz pepela dobijenog spaljivanjem mulja sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadne vode. Kod svih analiziranih uzoraka, koncentracija oksalne kiseline ima neznatan uticaj na vrijednost stepena ekstrakcije fosfora iz muljnog pepela pri vremenu ekstrakcije od 240 minuta, i odnosu L/S od 20/1. Optimalni uslovi za ekstrakciju fosfora iz muljnog pepela su: odnos L/S od 20/1, vrijeme ekstrakcije od 240 minuta i koncentracija oksalne kiseline od 0,2 mol/dm³. Prisustvo drugih metala (gvožđe, aluminijum) u muljnom pepelu može imati uticaj na vrijednost efikasnosti ekstrakcije fosfora. Buduća istraživanja bi trebalo usmjeriti na mogućnosti primjene i drugih solvenata bezbjednih za životnu sredinu (limunska kiselina, sirćetna kiselina, duboki eutektički solventi...) za ekstrakciju fosfora iz muljnog pepela, kao i prevođenje fosfora u vidu materijala pogodnih za dalju poljoprivrednu ili industrijsku upotrebu.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results obtained in this study, it is possible to extract phosphorus from ash obtained by the mono-incineration of sludge from a wastewater treatment plant. For all analyzed samples, the concentration of oxalic acid has a negligible effect on the phosphorus extraction rate from the incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA) at an extraction time of 240 minutes and an L/S ratio of 20/1. The optimal conditions for phosphorus extraction from ISSA are: an L/S ratio of 20/1, an extraction time of 240 minutes, and an oxalic acid concentration of 0.2 mol/dm³. The presence of other metals (iron, aluminum) in the ISSA may impact the extraction efficiency of phosphorus. Future research should focus on the potential use of other environmentally safe solvents (citric acid, acetic acid, deep eutectic solvents, etc.) for phosphorus extraction from ISSA, as well as the conversion of phosphorus into materials suitable for further agricultural or industrial use.

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